

Volume 12, Issues 1 & 2, November, 2025

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

A Publication of

**THE DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY AND
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT,
FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES,
UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN,
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VOLUME 12, ISSUES 1&2, NOVEMBER, 2025

ISSN: 1596-4116

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A SURVEY OF FINANCIAL AND NON-FINANCIAL BENEFITS OF SMES' SUSTAINABLE WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) have been the major driver for job creation and financial benefits in the growth and development of the private sector economy. The objectives of the study were to determine the extent to which non-financial and financial benefits on the mediating practices of sustainable waste management by SMEs, the awareness level of sustainable waste management practices, the relationship between the environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices, and the relationship between the awareness of the hazard of unmanaged waste and sustainable waste management practices by SMEs. The ex post facto research design and the purposive sampling technique were used to evaluate the population size of the SMEs across the six selected states in the six geopolitical zones, including the FCT, Abuja. A total of 29,382 copies of questionnaires at a default number of 4,197 copies were administered per state. The descriptive statistics of frequency, percentage, standard deviation, and cross tabulation, and Spearman's rank correlation techniques were used to analyze the data obtained. The results indicate a strong positive correlation between the benefits of SMEs and a strong positive relationship between financial benefits and the adoption of sustainable waste management practices. While the non-financial benefits had a positive impact on the company's image and reputation as the recognized outcomes of sustainable waste management practices. The study concludes that there is a moderate level of awareness among SMEs regarding the hazards of unmanaged waste, and recommends that the government implement comprehensive education and training programs for SMEs to enhance awareness of sustainable waste management practices.*

Keywords: Waste, Waste Management, Sustainability, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

INTRODUCTION

Businesses are not sustainable when they do not have access to a conducive ecosystem and what it offers, which are clean water, a clear environment, clean air, and freedom from air-borne diseases caused by indiscriminate dumping of waste. Small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) have been the major driver for job creation in the private sector for both developed and developing economies of the world, including Nigeria. According to the World Bank (2020), “about 99% of an

estimated 19.3 million businesses in the European Union (EU) are made up of SMEs and employ about 65 million people, which is 2/3rd of all employment”. In a developing country like Nigeria, about 96% of Nigerian businesses are SMEs. Furthermore, they account for about 90% of the manufacturing/industrial sectors in the country, and it is believed to have contributed about 48% of the Gross Domestic Product” (FSS, 2020).

According to the Small and Medium Enterprises Agency of Nigeria

(SMEDAN),” SMEs are small-scale enterprises with ten to forty-nine employees with an annual turnover of five to forty-nine million Naira, while a medium-scale enterprise has fifty to one hundred and ninety-nine employees with an annual turnover of fifty to four hundred and ninety-nine million Naira (excluding land and buildings)”.

Despite the immense contribution of SMEs to the economic growth of countries, the problem of waste management is still a major issue that they contend with. The unwholesome waste disposal practices by SMEs are of great concern to households, environmentalists, and the government. Especially in an era where the issue of sustainability is being brought to the fore. Some of the unacceptable waste disposal management practices involve emptying waste into water bodies, indiscriminate and random disposal of waste, and littering of waste on roads. These practices are not in line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) – 6, which is aimed at ensuring the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. It is expected that businesses should operate in a manner in which the process of making profit or meeting their needs does not negatively impact the ability of future individuals/business to meet their needs. SMEs are likely to enjoy some benefits if they engage in proper waste management best practices by observing the necessary measures/recommendations that are required for effective waste management. Prior studies have examined waste management practices in Nigeria. Noiki, Afolalu, Yusuf, Emeteri, Ongbali, Oloyede, Joseph, and Banjo (2021) assessed the “impact of the current waste management practices in Nigeria”, and the study shows that the existing waste management methods adopted in Nigeria are ineffective, and a call for an all-inclusive waste management approach was made. While at the international level,

Woodard (2020) examined “waste management in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) – a barrier to developing circular cities”. The study concludes that legislation on the compulsory separation of dry recyclable materials and bio-waste should be introduced into law.

The consciousness of the need for a sustainable waste management practice and the promulgation of the Harmful Waste Decree 42 of 1988, as a result of the illegal dumping of toxic waste in Koko village, in Delta State. This further led to the establishment of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) in 1988, with the responsibility of environmental management and protection. Due to the demand for effective and efficient enforcement/regulations, the act establishing FEPA was replaced with the National Environment Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), charged with the responsibility of protecting and developing the environment, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable development of Nigeria’s natural resources in general. Environmentalists, researchers, the government, and other stakeholders are interested in knowing the drivers of sustainable waste management practices by SMEs. There is a paucity of data and research on the factors, whether financial or non-financial, that motivate SMEs in embarking on sustainable waste management practices.

This is the gap that this study was meant to bridge. Knowledge of these drivers would enable the various stakeholders to narrow their focus and put the right measures in place to encourage SMEs in practicing sustainable waste management. The objectives of the study determined the extent to which financial benefits mediate practices of sustainable waste management by SMEs; ascertain the extent to which

non-financial benefits mediate practices of sustainable waste management by SMEs; determine the awareness level of sustainability waste management practices among SMEs; establish the relationship between the environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices by SMEs; and determine the relationship between the awareness of the hazard of unmanaged waste and sustainable waste management practices by SMEs in Nigeria.

The tested hypotheses are: H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between financial benefits and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between non-financial benefits and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria. H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between awareness level and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria. H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria, and H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between the awareness of the hazards of unmanaged waste and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Waste management has been a global problem for the underdeveloped and developing nations of the world. Where waste materials are poorly managed, it compromises environmental quality and is dangerous to human health (Agbebaku, 2018; Nwosu & Chukwueloka, 2020). Waste, which is a product of living, can originate from municipal, industrial, family, individual, and developmental activities such as the activities of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (Oyebode, 2018).

The Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) of the United States of America states that "solid waste means any garbage or refuse, sludge from a wastewater treatment plant, water supply treatment plant, or air pollution control facility, and other discarded material, resulting from industrial, commercial, mining, and agricultural operations, and from community activities."

According to Kadafa (2017), solid wastes are the unfunctional and undesirable goods in a solid form resulting from society's activities. Organic matter constitutes about 60% to 80% of the total waste stream along with plastics, scrap metals, and nylon as major recyclable constituents (Oyebode, 201). The increase in the population, businesses, development, and standard of living, and the neglect by individuals and institutions to follow appropriate procedures and best practices in solid waste management have led to the exponential increase in solid waste across the country. This has also reflected negatively on human health and the surrounding environment (Alwan & Bachai, 2023).

Municipal solid waste (MSW) is all items from homes and businesses that people no longer have any use for. In the United States, it is commonly called trash or garbage, and rubbish in Britain. Examples of this kind of waste are: glass, wood, food, paper, plastic, textiles, metals, sanitary waste in septic tanks, and other wastes. When countries grow economically, it is a function of their productivity, and there cannot be productivity without the springing up of businesses.

The major challenge of developing countries like Nigeria is the management of their waste. There are no clear policies or a practical approach to relieve the state of nuisance caused by the indiscriminate disposal of solid waste. Little or no budget is made by the Federal or state government

to tackle the issue of waste management. Waste collection and disposal services are offered mainly by the public sector through the State governments and involvement of formal public-private participation (PPP) (Oyebode, 2018). The most that some states embark upon is the engagement of consultants or private waste disposal companies to help in the evacuation of solid waste. Most of these private

consultants do not have the capacity to meet the demands or the quantum of solid waste to be disposed of. Nigeria is one of Africa's leading producers of solid waste, generating approximately 32 million tons per year, of which only 20-30% gets collected (Bakare, 2019). Figure 1 shows the map of Nigeria and solid waste as one of the environmental problems that calls for urgent attention.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing different locations and environmental problems.

Source: Pona et al. (2021) and Majebi and Agbebaku (2024)

Fig 1: Shows the state of environmental problems across the country and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, the implications

and impacts of small and medium enterprises on sustainable waste management practices in Nigeria.

Table 1: Waste Generation and Composition in Some Selected Cities in Nigeria

City	Population	Tonnes/month	Density (kg/m ³)	Kg/capita/day
Lagos	8,029,200	255,556	294	0.63
Kano	3,228,700	156,676	290	0.56
Kaduna	1,48,900	114,433	320	0.58
Port Harcourt	1,053,900	117,825	300	0.60
Onitsha	509,500	84,137	310	0.53
Ibadan	307,840	135,391	330	0.51
Makurdi	249,500	24,242	340	0.48
Abuja	159,900	14,785	280	0.66
Nsukka	100,700	12,000	370	0.44

Source: Oyebode (2018).

Evaluation of municipal solid waste management for improved public health and environment in Nigeria, *European Journal of Advances in Engineering and Technology*. According to Bogoro and Babanyara (2011), between 35 and 50 per cent of the solid waste generated in most developing countries is not collected. They usually end up in illicit dump sites, open spaces, wastelands, and drainage areas. Nigeria is one of the largest countries on the continent of Africa with a population of over 225million people (Worldometer, 2023). According to the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics report (2023) in the second quarter of 2023, the unemployment, underemployment, youth unemployment, and youth underemployment rates are about 4.1%, 12.2%, 6.9% and 18.1%.

While nearly 133 million Nigerians are multidimensionally poor, the multidimensional poverty index (MPI) is placed at 0.257. The MPI measures the various deprivations experienced by poor people in their daily lives. The indicators capture health, education, living standards, shocks, and work. In 2022, the MPI shows that Nigerians who are poor experience over one quarter of all possible deprivations. Sixty-five (65%) of multidimensionally poor people are found in the North, thirty-five (35%) are found in the southern part of Nigeria. To fight unemployment and the prevailing poverty, Nigerians, especially the youths, have engaged themselves in a myriad of small businesses to survive.

Nigeria has over 36.9 million Micro, Small, and Medium Scale Enterprises (MSMEs), comprising 96.7% of all businesses in Nigeria. It is estimated that 67% of these businesses are owned by youths. Over 45% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is contributed by MSMEs, and in addition, they contribute to nearly 90% of the employment rate in the country. Despite the growth and contributions of SMEs in the

country, the solid waste produced by them is also on the increase. Nigerians have developed several ways of disposing of solid waste without taking into consideration the impact of some of these methods on the ecosystem.

OPEN BURNING: This is a method of waste disposal where the waste is consumed or set ablaze by fire. The danger of this method is the emission of Carbon dioxide (CO₂) being released into the atmosphere, which eats up the Ozone layer and increases the amount of gaseous emissions into the atmosphere. According to Ukala, Akaun, and Owamah (2020), Incineration reduces solid waste by thirty per cent (30%). (Ukala, Akaun & Owamah, 2020). The negative impact of open-air burning on the environment cannot be quantified. Open burning has the propensity of causing fire to creep into individual or state properties, thereby resulting in loss of life and property.

OPEN DUMPING: Open dumping has been a part and parcel of some communities in Nigeria. Major cities like Lagos, Abuja, Onitsha, and soon are not spared from the environmental menace. This is the act of disposing of refuse indiscriminately. The sight of open dumping is an eyesore, and governments both at the state and national levels seem to be overwhelmed in tackling or nipping this menace in the bud.

LANDFILL: Landfills are designed to concentrate the waste in compacted layers to lessen the amount of both gaseous and liquid effluent to protect the environment. It is one of the most hygienic and cheapest methods of solid waste disposal; the apparent challenge with this method is the emission of methane and carbon dioxide gases into the atmosphere (Ukala, 2020). The waste is positioned in an engineered area with safeguards to ensure that the ground or soil is not contaminated (Osikabor, Adeleye & Oyelami, 2022). This method remains one of the cheapest

forms of waste disposal by SMEs because it is more financially convenient for them. Due to the presence of non-biodegradable items that are often found in the disposed of waste of some SMEs, this method may likely pose a serious health challenge to humans and animals.

INCINERATION: Waste incineration involves the use of high-temperature furnaces designed to combust/burn waste and diminish its volume by 95% and mass by 80-85%. This method is often encouraged in countries that have very little land area

and water tables close to the surface. In Nigeria, states like Lagos, Rivers, and Delta state have water tables close to the earth's surface, and are encouraged to adopt this means of solid waste disposal. In the European Union (EU), an increasing quantity and proportion of Solid Waste is being incinerated for the purpose of generating energy, though there are concerns about the impact of incineration on the climate. According to Eurostat, there were 70 million tonnes of municipal solid waste incinerated in 2017, which is 118 more than in 1995.

Figure 2: Incineration System
Source: Future Learn (2023).

The incineration process shows the waste disposal truck dumping the waste in the waste storage pit. Thereafter, a crane lifts the waste and drops it into the burning furnace. Below the burning furnace are water and ash that collect the residue from the furnace. The end process does not eliminate the waste; part of it is released into the atmosphere as water vapor and other vents, including dioxins. The leftover noncombustible elements, metals, and salts are left in the ash, which is later disposed of. The downside is the remnant of waste that still has to be disposed of in a landfill. The process, despite the huge cost involved, does not eliminate waste.

In developed climates, waste incinerators are a means of generating electricity; the electricity generated is a by-product of the incineration process. Despite this innovation, there are still concerns about the inability of the system to totally burn/destroy dioxins and furans produced when plastic materials are burned. It is believed that these compounds are cancer-causing agents. According to Futurelearn.com, carbon dioxide (CO₂) produced by landfill disposal of waste is higher than that produced by incineration of waste.

It posits that waste landfilled produces methane and a small amount of CO₂, and

methane not utilized for the generation of power has greater greenhouse emissions because methane is thirty-four times more potent than CO₂ as a greenhouse gas. So, the same ton of MSW would have a greater greenhouse effect if it were landfilled and not incinerated. Though it has its downsides, its benefits far outweigh its demerits.

COMPOSTING: Composting is a process of recycling organic wastes such as leaves, grass clippings, and fruit and vegetable scraps by putting them in an open pile or container and allowing them to decay through microbial action to generate compost, a dark-brown product that can be used as a soil conditioner. Composting yard waste yields fertilizer that replenishes the soil's nutrients. Composting also cuts the volume of yard waste by 50% to 70%. (Wilson & Feucht, 2011). When yard waste is collected separately at the household level, composting can be beneficial. Stringent air and water pollution regulations, as well as numerous waste disposal requirements, have accelerated the development of yard waste composting as a viable waste management option where tropical plants can thrive all year. Yard waste management issues can be solved by collecting, processing, and composting them as efficiently as possible. Composting yard waste has a lot of advantages, which include: lowering the cost of waste disposal, natural resource conservation, and creating a useful soil amendment, fog, acidulated precipitation, acid rain, and ozone layer depletion due to aerosol emissions into the atmosphere. (Barrett and Lawlor, 1995; Foday et al., 2013; Lekan & Charles, 2017).

WASTE MANAGERS: Another means employed by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in disposing of solid waste is by engaging waste disposal agencies.

BENEFITS OF WASTE MANAGEMENT: There are so many benefits that can be derived from

adopting a sustainable waste management system. Some of the financial and non-financial benefits of sustainable waste management systems are:

PROVISION OF ENERGY: Energy produced from the incineration of waste can be stored and transferred to the national grid. In some

COST SAVINGS: One of the main benefits of sustainable waste management is cost savings. Money-saving opportunities arise from reducing the amount of waste created and reusing or recycling materials. For example, businesses can save money by reducing the amount of packaging they use and recycling materials like cardboard and plastic. Further, companies can save money on maintenance and operating costs by using fewer resources, such as energy and water.

IMPROVED ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH: Reducing pollution and dangerous chemicals is a crucial goal of sustainable waste management. Reusing materials can reduce the need for new resources, which helps protect the environment from the impacts of resource extraction. Sustainable waste management can also improve air and water quality, improving communities' health.

ECONOMIC GAINS: Sustainable waste management can create economic gains, including more waste management opportunities, increased tax revenue for local governments, and support for local businesses. For example, companies focusing on waste reduction, reuse, and recycling can create more jobs in their communities, and local governments can receive more tax revenue from businesses reducing their waste. Lastly, businesses that focus on sustainable waste management

can support local businesses by buying locally produced and recycled products.

IMPROVED COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT: Sustainable waste management practices can also increase community engagement. Communities can become more engaged with waste management by providing better access to recycling and composting resources, educating citizens about sustainable practices, and encouraging participation in green initiatives.

ENHANCED RESOURCE EFFICIENCY: Reusing and repurposing materials is a Sustainable waste management practice that can reduce the need for new resources and help conserve materials. Recycling materials like paper, plastic, and metal can also help save resources and reduce the need for new resources.

IMPROVED HEALTH AND SAFETY: Sustainable waste management can also improve health and safety. Reducing the number of toxic chemicals in the environment can help reduce the risks of health problems. Additionally, lowering the amount of waste generated can reduce the number of pests and disease-carrying organisms. Improving air and water quality can also lead to improved health and safety.

POSITIVE SOCIAL IMPACTS: Sustainable waste management can also have positive social impacts. These impacts include increased civic pride, improved quality of life, and more equal distribution of resources. Improving air and water quality can improve the quality of life for citizens. Lastly, more efficient use of resources can lead to more equal distribution of resources, which can help reduce poverty. Others include: tax breaks and incentives, increased access to grants, and reduced insurance premiums. Businesses that reduce

their waste can qualify for tax breaks and incentives from

local governments. Additionally, businesses that focus on sustainable waste management can access grants to help cover the costs of sustainable practices.

METHODOLOGY

Both primary and secondary data collection were employed to facilitate the research. The primary source comprised mainly of field observations, interviews, and questionnaire administration. The secondary data explored were sourced from documentary materials and established sources. Since the research was purely experimental, data from primary sources were mainly relied on for the study. The data obtained were both quantitative and qualitative. The study made use of the survey design. Thus, according to the most recent survey conducted in 2017 by the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), there are about seventy-three thousand and eighty-one (73,081) SMEs in Nigeria, broken into 71,288 small enterprises and 1,793 medium enterprises.

The population of the study is twenty-nine thousand three hundred and eighty-two (29,382) SMEs in the six (6) states selected from the six geopolitical zones of the country. The purposive sampling technique was adopted in arriving at the sample size of the study. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 25 (SPSS) software. The primary data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and cross tabulation, while the inferential statistics used Spearman’s rank order correlation. The Spearman’s rank model specification used for the study is:
SWM = f (FB, NF, AL, EL, AH)
.....(1)

The econometric form of the above model (1) is:

SWM= β₁ + β₂FB+ β₃ NF+ β₃AL+ β₄EL+ β₅AH+ ε..... (2)

Where: SWM (sustainable waste management); FB (financial benefit); NF (Non-financial benefit); AL (Awareness level); EL (Environmental laws); AH

(Awareness of the hazards of unmanaged waste)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, results are presented and discussed in the light of the research findings. First, a set of descriptive statistics is presented, followed by the Spearman correlation results.

RESEARCH QUESTION 1

Table 2: The extent to which financial benefits mediate practices of sustainable waste management

Table with 3 columns: Question, Mean, Std. dev. It contains 5 rows of data regarding financial benefits and employee awareness.

Source: Output of data analysis using Stata 17

Respondents, on average, perceive financial benefits, such as cost savings and resource efficiency, as tangible outcomes of their sustainable waste management practices, as indicated by the mean of 3.954. The standard deviation of 0.843 suggests variability in responses, indicating diverse perceptions of the tangibility of financial benefits. On average, respondents agree that financial benefits derived from sustainable waste management practices contribute positively to their company's overall performance, as indicated by the mean of 3.986. The standard deviation of 0.777 suggests relatively consistent agreement among respondents on this contribution. The mean score of 3.553 suggests a moderate

agreement that the expectation of financial benefits influences the business's decision-making regarding the adoption of sustainable waste management practices. The high standard deviation of 1.112 indicates variability in responses, suggesting different perceptions of the influence of financial benefits on decision-making. On average, respondents strongly agree that financial gains play a significant role in driving their company's commitment to sustainable waste management practices, as indicated by the high mean of 4.005. The low standard deviation of 0.614 suggests relatively consistent agreement among respondents on the significant role of financial gains.

The mean score of 3.951 indicates a moderate agreement that employee awareness of the financial benefits enhances their engagement in sustainable waste management efforts. The standard deviation of 0.638 suggests relatively consistent agreement among respondents on the positive influence of employee awareness.

HYPOTHESIS 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between financial benefits and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria

Spearman's rho = 0.5631
Prob > t = 0.0000

In hypothesis testing, particularly with Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, the reported values typically provide insights into the strength and significance of the relationship between variables. The positive value of Spearman's rho (0.5631) suggests a strong positive correlation. This means that as financial benefits increase, there is a tendency for sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria to also increase. The extremely small p-value (0.0000) indicates strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H₀₁) that there is no significant relationship between financial benefits and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria as presented in Table 2.

RESEARCH QUESTION 2

Table 3: Extent to which non-financial benefits mediate practices of sustainable waste management by SMEs in Nigeria

Question	Mean	Std. dev.
Sustainable waste management practices contribute positively to our business's image and reputation.	3.599455	.9115529
Our business actively engages in sustainable waste management practices, such as recycling and waste reduction.	3.594005	1.257227
Non-financial benefits, such as improved community relations and positive employee perceptions, are observable outcomes of our sustainable waste management practices.	3.550409	1.136596
Do you believe that the non-financial benefits of experience play a significant role in sustaining our commitment to sustainable waste management practices?	4.122616	.576124
Business faces significant challenges or barriers in the implementation of sustainable waste management practices.	3.583106	.9879261

Source: Output of data analysis using Stata 17

Table 3 shows the descriptive statistics to determine the extent to which financial benefits mediate practices of sustainable waste management by SMEs in Nigeria. The mean score of 3.599 regarding question one indicates a moderate agreement among respondents that sustainable waste management positively contributes to the business's image and reputation. The

standard deviation of 0.912 suggests some variability in responses, with some participants showing stronger or weaker agreement. With a mean score of 3.594, concerning question two, there is a moderate agreement that the business actively engages in sustainable waste management practices. The higher standard deviation of 1.257 suggests more variability

in responses, indicating diverse opinions or experiences among respondents regarding the business's level of engagement.

On question three, the mean score of 3.550 reflects a moderate agreement that non-financial benefits, such as community relations and employee perceptions, are observable outcomes of sustainable waste management practices. The standard deviation of 1.137 indicates variability in responses, suggesting that different SMEs may experience and perceive non-financial benefits to varying extents. Respondents strongly agree (mean score of 4.123) on question four that non-financial benefits play a significant role in sustaining their commitment to sustainable waste management practices. The low standard deviation of 0.576 suggests that respondents generally share a high level of agreement on the importance of non-financial benefits.

The mean score of 3.583 regarding question five indicates a moderate agreement that businesses face significant challenges or barriers in implementing sustainable waste management practices. The standard deviation of 0.988 suggests variability in the perceived level of challenges among respondents. The results indicate a generally positive perception of

the relationship between sustainable waste management practices and various aspects of business, including image, engagement, non-financial benefits, and the belief in their significance. However, there is some variability in responses, particularly in perceptions of engagement and challenges, highlighting the diversity of experiences and opinions among SMEs in Nigeria regarding sustainable waste management.

HYPOTHESIS 2

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between non-financial benefits and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria

Spearman's rho =	0.1634
Prob > t =	0.0017

In hypothesis testing, particularly with Spearman's rho, the reported values typically provide insights into the strength and significance of the relationship between variables. In this case, the study reported Spearman's rho value is 0.1634 with a corresponding probability (p-value) of 0.0017. The statistical analysis provides evidence that contradicts the null hypothesis (H₀₂). Instead, suggesting that there is a statistically significant relationship between non-financial benefits and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria as presented in Table 3.

RESEARCH QUESTION 3

Table 4: Non-financial benefits mediate practices of sustainable waste management by SMEs in Nigeria

Question	Mean	Std. dev.
Familiar with the concept of sustainable waste management practices.	3.978202	.8195454
Aware of the environmental impact of improper waste management.	4.002725	.6993308
Aware of waste reduction strategies, such as minimizing packaging and promoting reusable products.	3.74659	.9686806
Knowledgeable about the environmental laws and regulations related to waste management in Nigeria.	3.749319	1.233567
Our business has implemented initiatives to educate employees about sustainable waste management practices.	3.711172	.6722123

Source: Output of data analysis using Stata 17

Respondents, on average, are fairly familiar with the concept of sustainable waste management practices, as indicated by the mean of 3.978. The low standard deviation (0.820) suggests that there is relatively less variability among respondents regarding their familiarity with sustainable waste management practices. On average, respondents are quite aware of the environmental impact of improper waste management, with a mean score of 4.003. The low standard deviation (0.699) indicates that there is relatively less variability in responses regarding awareness of environmental impact. Respondents, on average, have a moderate level of awareness of waste reduction strategies, such as minimizing packaging and promoting reusable products (mean of 3.747).

The standard deviation (0.969) suggests that there is more variability in responses, indicating diverse levels of awareness among respondents. On average, respondents have a moderate level of knowledge about the environmental laws and regulations related to waste management in Nigeria (mean of 3.749). The relatively high standard deviation (1.234) indicates more variability in responses, suggesting varying levels of knowledge among participants. On average, businesses have implemented initiatives to educate employees about sustainable waste

management practices, with a mean score of 3.711. The low standard deviation (0.672) suggests that there is relatively less variability in responses regarding the implementation of employee education initiatives.

HYPOTHESIS 3

H03: There is no significant relationship between awareness level and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria

Spearman's rho =	0.9178
Prob > t =	0.0038

The high value of Spearman's rho (0.9178) suggests a strong positive correlation. This implies that as awareness levels increase, there is a tendency for sustainable waste management practices to also increase among SMEs in Nigeria. The small p-value (0.0038) indicates that there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H02) that there is no significant relationship between awareness level and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria. This implies that SMEs with higher awareness levels tend to engage more actively in sustainable waste management practices. The strong correlation provides evidence for the importance of awareness in influencing and driving sustainable waste management efforts among these businesses as presented in Table 4.

Research Question 3

Table 5: Relationship between the environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices by SMEs in Nigeria

Question	Mean	Std. dev.
Aware of the environmental laws and regulations related to waste management in Nigeria.	3.561308	1.239569
Compliance with environmental laws is essential for sustainable waste management practices in our company.	3.885559	.9131604
Environmental laws have influenced the adoption of sustainable waste management practices in our company.	3.264305	1.213947
Complying with environmental laws poses challenges to the effective implementation of sustainable waste management practices in our company.	3.882834	.6485837
Government support and incentives for compliance with environmental laws positively influence our company's commitment to sustainable waste management practices.	3.940054	.5548623

Source: Output of data analysis using Stata 17

The mean score of 3.561 indicates a moderate level of awareness among respondents about environmental laws and regulations related to waste management in Nigeria. The relatively high standard deviation of 1.240 suggests variability in responses, indicating diverse levels of awareness among SMEs. Respondents, on average, agree that compliance with environmental laws is essential for sustainable waste management practices in their companies, as indicated by the mean of 3.886. The standard deviation of 0.913 suggests relatively less variability in responses, indicating a more consistent agreement on the importance of compliance. The mean score of 3.264 suggests a moderate agreement that environmental laws have influenced the adoption of sustainable waste management practices in respondents' companies. The standard deviation of 1.214 indicates variability in responses, suggesting that different SMEs have different perceptions of the influence of environmental laws. On average, respondents agree that complying with environmental laws poses challenges to the effective implementation of sustainable waste management practices

(mean of 3.883). The low standard deviation of 0.649 indicates relatively consistent agreement among respondents on this aspect. Respondents, on average, agree that government support and incentives for compliance with environmental laws positively influence their company's commitment to sustainable waste management practices, as indicated by the mean of 3.940. The low standard deviation of 0.555 suggests relatively consistent agreement on the positive influence of government support and incentives.

HYPOTHESIS 4

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria.

Spearman's rho =	0.3055
Prob > t =	0.0000

The reported value is 0.3055. In this case, 0.3055 suggests a positive but moderate correlation between environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria. The p-value (Prob > |t|) is reported as 0.0000. The extremely small p-value

(0.0000) indicates strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H04) that there is no significant relationship between environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices among

SMEs in Nigeria. This means that as awareness of and adherence to environmental laws increase, there is a tendency for sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria to also increase as presented in Table 5.

RESEARCH QUESTION 4

Table 6: Relationship between the awareness of the hazard of unmanaged waste and sustainable waste management practices by SMEs in Nigeria

Question	Mean	Std. dev.
Well-informed about the environmental and health hazards associated with unmanaged waste.	3.942779	1.045153
Believe that unmanaged waste poses significant risks to our community and environment.	3.980926	.7976511
Awareness of the hazards of unmanaged waste influences our company's commitment to sustainable waste management practices.	3.86921	.8958344
Implementing sustainable waste management practices is an effective way to mitigate the hazards associated with unmanaged waste.	4.095368	.5997771
The potential impact of unmanaged waste on employee health motivates our company to adopt sustainable waste management practices.	3.915531	.674236

Source: Output of data analysis using Stata 17

Respondents, on average, consider themselves well-informed about the environmental and health hazards associated with unmanaged waste, as indicated by the mean of 3.943. The standard deviation of 1.045 suggests variability in responses, indicating diverse levels of self-perceived knowledge among SMEs. On average, respondents believe that unmanaged waste poses significant risks to their community and the environment, as indicated by the mean of 3.981. The relatively low standard deviation of 0.798 suggests relatively consistent agreement among respondents on this belief. The mean score of 3.869 suggests a moderate agreement that awareness of the hazards of unmanaged waste influences the company's commitment to sustainable waste management practices.

The standard deviation of 0.896 indicates variability in responses, suggesting that different SMEs perceive different levels of influence. On average, respondents strongly agree that implementing sustainable waste management practices is an effective way to mitigate the hazards associated with unmanaged waste, as indicated by the high mean of 4.095. The low standard deviation of 0.600 suggests relatively consistent agreement among respondents on the effectiveness of practices. The mean score of 3.916 indicates a moderate agreement that the potential impact of unmanaged waste on employee health motivates the company to adopt sustainable waste management practices. The standard deviation of 0.674 suggests variability in responses, indicating diverse perceptions of the impact on employee health.

HYPOTHESIS 5

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between the awareness of the hazards of unmanaged waste and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria.

Spearman's rho =	0.416
Prob > t =	0.0000

The extremely small p-value (0.0000) indicates strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H₀₅) that there is no significant relationship between the awareness of hazards of unmanaged waste and sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria. The positive value of Spearman's rho (0.416) suggests a moderate positive correlation. This means that as awareness of the hazards of unmanaged waste increases, there is a tendency for sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria to also increase as presented in Table 6.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The survey conducted to explore the financial and non-financial benefits of sustainable waste management practices among SMEs in Nigeria has yielded valuable insights. The analysis of both financial and non-financial aspects provides a comprehensive understanding of the impact of these practices on businesses. The data reveal a strong positive relationship between financial benefits and the adoption of sustainable waste management practices. SMEs that actively engage in waste reduction, recycling, and resource efficiency report tangible financial gains, including cost savings and enhanced overall company performance.

Thus, the study concludes that both the financial and non-financial benefits mediate the practices of sustainable waste management by SMEs. Furthermore, there is an awareness level of sustainable waste

management practices among SMEs. In addition, there exists a relationship between the environmental laws and sustainable waste management practices by SMEs; and lastly, there exists a relationship between the awareness of the hazard of unmanaged waste and sustainable waste management practices by SMEs in Nigeria.

The study therefore made the following recommendations.

The government should implement comprehensive education and training programs for SMEs to enhance awareness of both the financial and non-financial benefits of sustainable waste management practices. This can empower businesses to make informed decisions and engage employees in environmentally responsible practices.

Secondly, there should be an advocate for increased government support and incentives for SMEs actively involved in sustainable waste management. This support can further motivate businesses to prioritize environmental sustainability and overcome challenges in implementation.

Thirdly, the government should put in place viable community engagement initiatives to showcase the positive impact of sustainable waste management practices. Building positive relations with the community can enhance the reputation of SMEs and contribute to long-term success.

Fourthly, the government and other stakeholders should encourage a culture of continuous improvement in waste management practices. SMEs should explore innovative solutions and technologies to further enhance both financial and non-financial outcomes.

In addition, there should be collaboration with regulatory bodies to develop strategies that address challenges in legal compliance. Creating a supportive framework can ease the implementation of sustainable waste management practices while ensuring adherence to environmental laws.

Lastly, the establishment of employee recognition programs to acknowledge and reward contributions to sustainable waste

management practices. This can boost employee engagement and foster a sense of pride in contributing to the company's environmental and social responsibility.

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